

Copper based heterostructures for carbon dioxide reduction to energy products by photo- and photo-electro catalysis

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Carbon dioxide capture and utilization-CCU is a strategic technology for stepping away from fossil-carbon through carbon recycling [1]. Various methods for CO₂ utilization, including photocatalysis, are actively researched as promising, environmentally friendly approaches for converting solar energy into chemical energy.

Copper-based materials stand out among heterogeneous photocatalysts due to their high photoactivity under visible light, low toxicity, and the abundance of copper. Our investigation focused on copper-copper and copper-zinc heterostructures [2], demonstrating activity in the reduction of carbon dioxide within photocatalytic and photoelectrochemical systems. The primary objective was to explore the fate of photogenerated charge carriers, influencing crucial properties like long-term activity, efficiency, and stability.

Achieving a comprehensive understanding of photo(electro)catalysis demands a holistic insight into the interface. To address this challenge, a multidimensional approach was employed, utilizing various techniques such as classic electrochemical methods, photoelectrochemical measurements, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy, and other spectroscopic tools, including synchrotron-based techniques [3]. This holistic investigation methodology provided a thorough understanding of the materials' behaviour in terms of both stability and activity.

Through this comprehensive approach, we examined copper/copper and copper/zinc heterostructures in both photocatalytic and photoelectrochemical systems. Our target reactions included the reduction of water to hydrogen and the reduction of carbon dioxide to C₁ and C₂ molecules. This integrated investigation sheds light on the intricate processes of charge separation, recombination, transfer, and trapping, contributing valuable insights for the development of efficient and stable photocatalytic systems.

References

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